

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aromatic acetals by N-chloronicotinamide in acetonitrile medium

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Abstract : An effort has been made to introduce N-chloronicotinamide (NCN) as an oxidant to some aromatic acetals. The reaction shows total first order kinetics, zero order in [acetal] and first order in [NCN]. Increase in ionic strength has marginal effect on the rate while increase in dielectric constant of the medium decreases the rate. Further the rate is slightly decreased by the addition of nicotinamide. Arrhenius parameters and activation parameters are calculated. A mechanism consistent with the observation is proposed and an appropriate rate law is derived.

Keywords : Aromatic acetals, N-chloronicotinamide, kinetics, mechanism.

Introduction

The biological importance of acetal proved from its perfumery action¹, precursors of acidic drugs², role in bioorganic research in exploring antibacterial³, antiviral⁴, and anticancer activities are the center of attention to study the present work. Acetals find extensive applications in aerosols, as solvent in agrochemicals, solvent in cosmetics, useful tool in organic synthesis and also as solvent in veterinary medicines. Earlier publications reported the rearrangement of aromatic acetals^{5,6}. It was reported that aromatic acetals when treated with boron trifluoride etherate give benzyl allyl ether⁷. Though much oxidation kinetics has been done on aliphatic acetals by N-chlorosaccharin⁸, N-chlorobenzamide⁹, lead(IV) acetate¹⁰, only few reported in aromatic acetals¹¹⁻¹⁵ and extensive literature survey reveal that there is up-to-date review articles on the kinetic studies of NCN on acetals. The pharmacological effect of NCN¹⁶ shows significant locomotor activity, but its application in the field of oxidation kinetics is very much limited to compounds like chalcones¹⁷, benzyl ethers¹⁸, aromatic aldehydes¹⁹, amino acids²⁰, S-phenyl-mercaptoacetic acid²¹ and alcohols²². Hence we report herein the results of kinetics and mechanistic investigation on the oxidation of six aromatic acetals by NCN in acetonitrile with the view to probe the mecha-

nism of oxidation.

Results and discussion

NCN oxidation of all the six aromatic acetals studied exhibits similar kinetic behavior. A first order dependence of reaction rate on [NCN] is observed. The rate constants k_{obs} remains nearly constant at several initial [NCN] which further confirms the first order dependence on [NCN]. The rate constants are computed from the linear plots of $\log [NCN]$ against time. The first order rate constant shows no variation with increase in [acetal] and the order of the reaction in acetal is zero. The observed zero order dependence is further confirmed by the fact that substituent has no effect on the rate of oxidation and is independent of the nature and concentration of acetal. The first order rate constants for benzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal are given in Table 1 as representative data.

The addition of 0.2 M sodium perchlorate does not produce considerable increase in rate. This indicates the involvement of ion-dipole species in the rate determining step.

To characterize more fully the transition state, the rate of acetal cleavage by NCN is studied in several solvent mixtures. Dielectric constant of the reaction is altered by the addition of water in varying proportions

Table 1. Rate constants of oxidations of benzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal by NCN at 323 K

[NaClO ₄ .H ₂ O] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M, CH ₃ CN = 95%		
10 ³ [NCN] (M)	10 ² [C ₆ H ₅ CH(OR) ₂] (M)	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)
4.0	6.0	3.18
5.0	6.0	3.19
6.0	6.0	3.20
7.0	6.0	3.21
8.0	6.0	3.20
9.0	6.0	3.17
4.0	5.0	3.15
4.0	6.0	3.18
4.0	7.0	3.18
4.0	8.0	3.19
4.0	9.0	3.20
4.0	10.0	3.21

(v/v). The rate of the reaction decreases with increase in dielectric permittivity of the medium (*D*) (Table 2).

For ion-dipole reactions²³,

$$\ln k = \ln k_0 + \frac{LZe^2}{8\pi D_0 D_s RT} \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r^\#} \right)$$

where *k*₀ is a function of *D*₀, *L* = 6.02 × 10²³, *Ze* is charge of ion, *T* is absolute temperature in Kelvin and *r* is the distance of approach of the dipole. The equation pre-

dicts the linear relation between log *k* and 1/*D*. The plot of log *k*_{obs} against 1/*D* of the medium is a straight line with positive slope. As it is well known ion-dipole and dipole-dipole reactions are accelerated in presence of low dielectric solvent^{24, 25} is evidenced in the present investigation.

Added chloride ion has marginal effect on the rate of the reaction. Hence it excludes chlorine as the effective oxidizing species. The rate of the reaction has slight retardation with increase in [nicotinamide].

Exclusion of free radical intermediates :

Some attempts were made to capture free radical intermediates by using suitable trapping agents. Observable precipitation of acrylonitrile polymer²⁶ or reduced rates of oxidation with added acrylonitrile have been cited as evidence for free radical reactions. However no polymerization of acrylonitrile could be detected under any of the reaction conditions used in our kinetic studies. Hence the participation of free radical intermediates in this reaction is excluded.

In order to evaluate Arrhenius and activation parameters, experiments are carried out in the temperature range of 313 K to 333 K and the first order rate constants are calculated. The Arrhenius parameters are evaluated by plotting log *k*_{obs} vs 1/*T* and using Eyring equation the activation parameters are calculated (Table 3). The nega-

Table 2. Effect of varying solvent composition on NCN oxidation of benzaldehyde acetals at 323 K

CH ₃ CN-H ₂ O (%)	[C ₆ H ₅ CH(OR) ₂] = 6.0 × 10 ⁻² M, [NCN] = 4.0 × 10 ⁻³ M, [NaClO ₄ .H ₂ O] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M					
	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)					
	R = Ethyl	R = Propyl	R = Butyl	R = Isobutyl	R = Isoamyl	R = Benzyl
95-5	3.42	3.35	3.18	2.95	3.59	3.61
94-6	1.60	1.51	1.60	1.50	1.74	1.97
93-7	0.83	0.81	0.85	0.84	0.88	0.89
92-8	0.39	0.42	0.41	0.41	0.47	0.49
91-9	0.21	0.23	0.19	0.19	0.26	0.27
90-10	0.13	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.14	0.15

Table 3. Effect of temperature on the rate constants and values of activation parameters

C ₆ H ₅ CH(OR) ₂	[C ₆ H ₅ CH(OR) ₂] = 6 × 10 ⁻² M, [NCN] = 4 × 10 ⁻³ M, [NaClO ₄ .H ₂ O] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M, CH ₃ CN = 95%						Δ <i>H</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> [#] (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	log <i>A</i>
	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)								
	313 K	318 K	323 K	328 K	333 K	<i>E</i> _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)			
R = Ethyl	1.08	2.02	3.42	4.89	7.45	82.41	79.72	-28.28	14.82
R = Propyl	1.18	2.06	3.35	4.99	7.64	80.17	77.48	-31.36	14.46
R = Butyl	1.13	1.98	3.18	4.98	7.29	80.70	77.84	-31.07	14.53
R = Isobutyl	1.04	1.64	2.95	4.57	7.28	82.27	79.59	-28.99	14.76
R = Isoamyl	1.26	2.14	3.59	5.34	8.12	80.51	77.83	-30.65	14.55
R = Benzyl	1.28	2.20	3.61	5.57	8.29	80.93	78.25	-30.05	14.62

tive entropy of activation suggests a greater orderliness in the transition state of the reaction. The nearly same free energy of activation suggested a probably similar mechanism is operative in the oxidation of all the acetals studied.

Mechanism :

Under the experimental conditions the possible oxidizing species are Cl^+ , NCN , Cl_2 , HOCl and H_2OCl^+ in acetonitrile-water mixture. The first order dependence of rate on $[\text{NCN}]$ and the slight retarding effect of nicotinamide indicate that NCN may not be the reactive species. The marginal effect due to sodium perchlorate precludes the involvement of protonated species of the oxidant. Since there is no effect due to Cl^- the possibilities of involvement of Cl_2 is ruled out. In view of the above observations, HOCl is considered as the probable oxidizing species²⁷ in the following reaction sequence and a plausible mechanism rationalizing the observed kinetic data is proposed.

Applying steady state approximation to $[\text{HOCl}]$ and [complex],

$$\frac{-d[\text{NCN}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{NCN}] [\text{acetal}]}{(k_{-2} + k_3) k_{-1} [\text{NA}] + k_2 [\text{acetal}]}$$

The above rate expression satisfactorily explains the retarding effect of $[\text{NA}]$ and first order dependence of $[\text{NCN}]$. Since $[\text{NA}]$ has slight retarding effect, $\{k_{-1} [\text{NA}] \ll k_2 [\text{acetal}]\}$ $k_{-1} [\text{NA}]$ is ignored.

The rate law is given as

$$\frac{-d[\text{NCN}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_3 [\text{NCN}]}{(k_{-2} + k_3)}$$

The above rate law accounts for the first order dependence of NCN and zero order dependence of acetal.

A similar mechanism was earlier discussed by Gopalakrishnan²⁸. The above mechanism involving simultaneous loss of H^+ from an α -carbon and an electron pair from ether oxygen has been well supported by Deno and Potter²⁹ and also evidenced in monoethers³⁰. The values of activation parameters supported the proposed mechanism. The large negative entropy of activation supported the above mechanism³¹ and also in order to establish HOCl as the reactive species, kinetic experiments were carried out with NCN and HOCl under comparable conditions. The kinetic data with HOCl and NCN were same. Hence it might be the active oxidizing species³². A decrease in the rate with increasing dielectric permittivity (D) of the medium also supports the proposed mechanism³³. The reaction is not susceptible to ionic strength variation evidencing the conclusion drawn from the solvent effect studies.

Experimental

All liquor organic compounds were purified by distillation. Solid organic compounds (K. Fluka and K. Laboratories Koch-Light) were of extra pure variety. NCN was prepared from the standard procedures³⁴ and its purity was checked by iodometric assay of its active chlorine content and also by its ^1H NMR spectra. The substrates used benzaldehyde di-*n*-ethyl acetal, benzaldehyde di-*n*-propyl acetal, benzaldehyde di-*n*-butyl acetal, benzaldehyde di-*iso*-butyl acetal, benzaldehyde di-*iso*-amyl acetal and benzaldehyde di-benzyl acetal were prepared by the standard procedure and their purities were checked by usual methods.

A concentrated aqueous sodium perchlorate was used to maintain a high ionic strength to swamp the reaction mixture. The reaction was initiated by the addition of requisite amounts of NCN to a mixture of prethermostated acetal, sodium perchlorate, water and acetonitrile at desired temperature (i.e. at 50°C). The kinetics was carried out in 95% acetonitrile-5% water mixtures. Under pseudo-first order conditions keeping the substrate always in excess, oxidation rates were monitored titrimetrically.

Product analysis and stoichiometric study :

Ten ml of 0.02 M solution of NCN in acetonitrile was added to 40 ml of 0.04 M solution of acetal in acetonitrile. This solution was thermostated for one hour. Then the solution was diluted with water and excess of NCN was carefully removed with sodium thiosulphate solution. The resulting aqueous solution was extracted with ether and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent ether was removed and the product ester was identified by TLC, IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

The reaction mixture containing excess of NCN over acetal (3 : 1) in the presence of NaClO₄ was kept at the room temperature for 36 h. Estimation of unutilized NCN showed that one mole of the acetal reacted with one mole of NCN. The overall stoichiometry of the reaction may be represented as

R = Substituent (ethyl, propyl, butyl, isobutyl, isoamyl and benzyl)

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